

EDITORIAL MESSAGE**Celebrating the 60th Anniversary of Florentin Smarandache**

December 10, 2014, marked the 60th anniversary of Florentin Smarandache's birth. Through great personal sacrifice, our friend and colleague became one of the co-founders, and Executive Editor of our journal *Progress in Physics*. He is a mathematician of international renown, and a Professor in the Department of Mathematics and Science at the University of New Mexico, where he was Department Chair for many years. His detailed biography was previously published one year ago, in our journal.*

We, the colleagues and friends who have been privileged to know Florentin closely, wish him a happy life for many decades to come, good health, prosperity, and enthusiasm for his further research.

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Prof. Florentin Smarandache,
Executive Editor of *Progress in Physics*

*Rabounski D. Florentin Smarandache: A Celebration. *Progress in Physics*, 2014, issue 1, 25–27.